

IAU General Assembly XXXII: IAUS 394 Post-Meeting Report

13 - 15 AUGUST 2024, CAPE TOWN SOUTH AFRICA

WEBSITE: <https://allinclusiveagn.saa0.ac.za/>

CHAIR: Dr Sarah V. White [she] (South African Astronomical Observatory [SAAO], South Africa)

CO-CHAIR: Dr Sthabile Kolwa [they/she] (University of Johannesburg, South Africa)

CO-CHAIR: Assoc. Prof. Preeti Kharb [she] (National Centre for Radio Astrophysics [NCRA], India)

SCIENTIFIC ORGANISING COMMITTEE MEMBERS:

Prof. Tao An [he] (Shanghai Astronomical Observatory [SHAO], China)

Prof. Sara Ellison [she] (University of Victoria, Canada)

Dr Vincenzo Mainieri [he] (European Southern Observatory [ESO], Germany)

Prof. Roberto Maiolino [he] (University of Cambridge, UK)

Dr Lucia Marchetti [she] (University of Cape Town, South Africa) – IAU Division-J representative

Dr Andrea Merloni [he] (Max Planck Institute for Extraterrestrial Physics [MPE], Germany)

Assoc. Prof. Leah Morabito [she] (Durham University, UK)

Dr Roderik Overzier [he] (Observatório Nacional, Brazil)

Dr Annalisa Pillepich [she] (Max Planck Institute for Astronomy [MPiA], Germany)

Prof. Mirjana Pović [she] (Space Science & Geospatial Institute [SSGI], Ethiopia/IAA-CSIC, Spain)

Prof. Elaine Sadler [she] (University of Sydney and CSIRO, Australia)

Assoc. Prof. Stas Shabala [he] (University of Tasmania, Australia)

Assoc. Prof. Ryan Trainor [he] (Franklin & Marshall College, US)

1. **MEETING IDENTIFICATION NUMBER:** Symposium 394
2. **MEETING TITLE:** All-inclusive AGN (Active Galactic Nuclei)
3. **COORDINATING DIVISION:** IAU Division J (Galaxies and Cosmology)
4. **LOCATION:** Cape Town, South Africa
5. **DATES OF SYMPOSIUM:** 13th-15th August 2024

6. LIST OF INVITED SPEAKERS AND THEIR ABSTRACTS:

We are delighted that each of our speaker invitations were accepted, with a gender balance of: 4 female speakers, 2 non-binary (or gender non-specific) speakers, and 4 male speakers.

- Invited review talk by **Prof. Roberto Assef [he]** (Universidad Diego Portales, Chile)
 - *The Host Galaxies of Luminous Quasars*
 - Luminous quasars are likely a key ingredient in the evolution of massive galaxies, either by producing accretion-disk powered outflows or radio jets that heat and/or blow out the gas from the ISM/CGM necessary to continue star-formation. Understanding the feedback mechanisms that operate requires detailed knowledge of the supermassive black holes (SMBHs) properties and their host galaxies, particularly in regards to the state of the ISM/CGM during intense SMBH accretion phases. While host galaxies of luminous quasars have been traditionally difficult to study at UV and optical wavelengths due to the brightness of the accretion disk in type-1 objects outshining the stellar emission, observatories like ALMA in the sub-millimeter and JWST in the near- and mid-infrared are allowing us to look with unprecedented detail into these questions. Furthermore, during the last decade, families of very luminous type-2 quasars have been identified. In these objects the host galaxy is much easier to characterize although the SMBH properties are more difficult to gauge. In this talk I will present a quick review of the state of host galaxies in luminous quasars, focusing particularly on the most luminous ones known where these effects are likely maximized.

- Discussion session on Indigenous Astronomy, Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion

Panel members: **Prof. Jarita Holbrook [she]** (The University of Edinburgh, UK)

- *Cultural Astronomy in Africa*
- Cultural Astronomy is interdisciplinary utilizing astronomy, understanding of particular cultures and their sky related arts, beliefs and practices. Horizon astronomy, the tropics, the equator and circumpolar stars are all important for understanding the specifics Indigenous Astronomy. Examples of Indigenous Knowledge / Indigenous Astronomy will be shown from across Africa. The relationship between Africans and the sky is ongoing, including the encounter of telescope astronomy. South Africa's investment in astronomy and astrophysics is commendable and the observing facilities are world class. The Square Kilometre Array radio telescope was the impetus for my study based in the Karoo focused on both Indigenous astronomy and how the SKA is being received by the local community. Clips from my film SKA ≥ Karoo Radio Telescope will be used to illustrate points about community expectations and economic benefit.

Prof. Debra Meyer [she] (Sol Plaatje University, South Africa)

- *Diversity and Equity in Science*
- Three decades of democracy and associated anti-apartheid legislation in South Africa does not translate to success in diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) in academia in general or the sciences in particular. Most national universities have policies that govern aspects of DEI but these can be circumvented and side-lined. Universities mostly monitor progress at faculty level allowing departmental underachievement to disappear in the summation and making it possible for research groups to operate under the policy monitoring radar. Historically disadvantaged groups have access to study and work opportunities, but this seldom goes along with consideration of the conditions necessary for their success. The stress of being part of a group assumed to be less than or not good enough means being constantly alert to subtle and overt

prejudice which can harm psychological well being, increase the chance of burnout, and deplete the drive needed to complete research projects successfully. The same systemic bias, reinforced by institutional and historical structures and value systems seen internationally is experienced nationally as well. Given the benefits of diversity in scientific endeavour including that it keeps scientific stagnation at bay, it's hard to understand why it's not more actively protected.

Prof. Prajval Shastri [they/she] (Raman Research Institute, India)

- *Degendering Physics in India: Why so slow?*
- It has been over a quarter of a century since attention was drawn to the evidence that the over-representation of men in the Indian physics enterprise is due to societal patriarchy leaching into academia which then results in gender-based discrimination within. Consequent acknowledgement of this phenomenon by the government, was also accompanied by significant funding resulting in a couple of laudable interventions. Progress has been slow, however, likely because several mitigative interventions sought to address only the symptoms and were themselves moulded by patriarchy. The Gender in Physics Working Group of the Indian Physics Association was launched with the vision of stepping away from the all-too-common “fixing-the-women” approach by drawing attention to the root causes of gender inequity. One of the outcomes was the Hyderabad Charter for Gender Equity in Physics, that seeks to address these systemic problems. Its recommendations are vindicated by several examples from the astrophysics enterprise globally. Some of these lessons will be described.

Associate Prof. Jorge Moreno [they/he] (Pomona College, US)

- *Astro Sequoia: a blueprint to decolonize research and mentoring in galaxy evolution*
- In this talk I will share a blueprint to create research directions and spaces that are more inclusive and challenge existing systems of domination. During the first part of the talk I will discuss how violent language has permeated the field of galaxy evolution, and I will share

lessons from Kichwa culture that can help us mitigate this. The second part will be devoted to this blueprint. Rather than adhering to traditional ways, we can create anti-hierarchical collectives where the most marginalized voices are prioritized. To achieve this, this blueprint implements the following key pillars: (1) justice education, (2) community town halls, (3) accountability systems, and (4) art. I will discuss effective ways to implement this blueprint across communities, wherein trust and mutual solidarity can be built.

and **Dr Alfredo Carpineti [he]** (Pride in STEM/IFLScience), who talked about his experience in EDI and his work to promote diverse voices in astronomy.

- Invited talk by **Dr Nicole Thomas [she]** (The University of Western Australia, Australia)
- *Radio galaxies in cosmological simulations*
- Radio galaxies are a population of active galactic nuclei (AGN) identified by the presence of relativistic jets observed at radio wavelengths. These radio galaxies play a key role in quenching and maintaining the quenched status of massive galaxies. While it is clear that these sources play an integral role in the evolution of galaxies, the physical processes describing the growth and feedback mechanisms of the central supermassive black holes are still poorly defined. SKA precursors, such as MeerKAT, are already providing new insights into the faint population of radio galaxies, challenging our understanding of their nature, prevalence, and impact across cosmic time. It is therefore vital that we have the means to interpret these observations in the context of the larger galaxy population and specifically, the ongoing black hole accretion and feedback processes on a cosmological scale.

In this talk I will discuss the current status of AGN growth and feedback in cosmological simulations and how we can combine these with semi-analytical models (SAMs) to improve predictions of the global host galaxy and black hole properties of radio galaxies over cosmic time. I will briefly test these predictions with the MIGHTEE survey, a radio continuum survey on the MeerKAT array, as a vital step in constraining, and therefore understanding, the physical mechanisms describing black hole growth and feedback.

- Invited talk by **Dr Dylan Nelson [he]** (University of Heidelberg, Germany)
 - *The impact of AGN feedback in cosmological galaxy formation simulations*
 - Feedback from supermassive black holes is an essential ingredient in all modern cosmological hydrodynamical simulations of galaxy formation. The energy released from these AGN reshapes the physical properties of galaxies, their gaseous halos, and the intergalactic medium itself. The impact of AGN feedback on observables, from the galaxy population to the large-scale cosmic web, can finally be captured in large-volume cosmological simulations of structure and galaxy formation. I will discuss some of the more interesting, and unexpected, findings from these simulations.
- Plenary talk (given remotely) by **Dr Beatriz Mingo [she]** (The Open University, UK)
 - *Multiwavelength classification in the age of Big Data*
 - Despite the success of the unified model in the past 30 years, AGN might still be the most over-classified objects in astronomy, with over 50 labels being commonly used to describe the phenomenon of gas accretion by a supermassive black hole. While we may be accused of over-enthusiasm when it comes to putting sources in boxes, not all AGN fall under the unification umbrella, and classifications can be useful to understand the complex physics involved in the AGN-galaxy co-evolution - as long as we use them sensibly. With ever-larger volumes of data being produced by new surveys, and the necessity to rely on automation, how should we approach future AGN classifications in a way that is physically meaningful and consistent across different wavelengths and instruments?
- Invited talk by **Dr Jan Scholtz [he]** (The University of Cambridge, UK)
 - *Search for AGN in the early Universe with JWST*

- With the first year of JWST data, AGN have been in the forefront of galaxy evolution, as an explanation of AGN early quiescent galaxies, stochastic star formation and their contribution to the re-ionisation of the Universe. In this talk, I give an overview of identification of AGN at high redshift with rest-frame UV and optical data, its challenges and a need for new photoionisation modelling. Finally, I will discuss the properties of AGN host galaxies, their co-evolution with galaxies and our current constraints on seeding of the supermassive black holes with AGN observations up to $z=11$.

7. LIST OF 180 PARTICIPANTS:

(after receiving 300+ abstracts)

Abraão Anta, Aditya J.N.H.S., Ahlam Farhan, Alberto Carramiñana,
 Alexander Plavin, Alfredo Carpineti, Allison Man, Anderson Caproni,
 Andrea Gokus, Andrzej Niedzwiecki, Anelise Audibert, Ann Njeri,
 Anna Lena Schaible, Anne-Kathrin Baczko, Antoine Mahoro, Areg Mickaelian,
 Ashkbiz Danekar, Atsushi Hoshi, Beatriz Mingo, Blessing Musiimenta,
 Bosco Oruru, Brenda Homera, Brian Bichang'a, Brooke Simmons,
 Bruno Lago, Catherine Witherspoon, Célestin Herbé-George,
 Christopher Hayward, Clara Pennock, Clare Wethers, Dan Schwartz,
 Daudi Mazengo, Dawei Xu, Debra Meyer, Dejene Woldeyes,
 Deokhyeong Lee, Dharam Lal, Donaji Esparza Arredondo, Dongsu Ryu,
 Dorcus Mulumba, Dr Proven-Adzri, Dylan Nelson, Eckhard Sturm,
 Elena Nokhrina, Eli Kasai, Elizabeth Kamau, Elizabeth Mahony,
 Emily Kerrison, Erandi Chavez, Erika Hornecker, Eslam Elhosseiny,
 Evaristus Iyida, Fabio Luchsinger, Farideh Mazoochi, Fatma Shaban,
 Feng-Yuan Liu, Filippo Marcello Maccagni, Georgios Filippas Paraschos,
 Gloria Raharimbolamena, Gourab Giri, Harris Yao Fortune Marc,
 Ignacio del Moral-Castro, Isreal Elijah, Ivan Kostrichkin, Izzy Garland,
 Jack Livingston, Jacques Smulders, Jahang Prathap P K, Jake Bennett,
 James Chibueze, James Rodi, Jan Scholtz, Janie du Preez,
 Jason Makechemu, Jaya Maithil, Jayde Bhana, JC Holbrook,
 Jin Zhang, Jiří Svoboda, Jochen Heidt, John Hood,
 Jones Chilufya, Jonny Pierce, Jordan Collier, Jorge Moreno,
 Josephine Chishala, Julius Mathew, Karina Santana, Kartik Sheth,
 Kathleen Charlton, Katlego Mogamisi, Keigo Fukumura, Khushboo Dixit,
 Laetitia Gibaud, Leon Mtshweni, Leon David Salas, Luigi Barchiesi,
 Luis Ho, Lyuba Slavcheva-Mihova, Mahdi Abdollahi, Marcin Glowacki,

Maria Stone, Marina Arnaudova, Matilde Signorini, Mauro Dadina,
 Mehbuba Ahmed, Mekuanint Kifle, Mfuphi Ntshatsha, Michal Zajacek,
 Mingyu Ryu, Miora Mbolatiana Randrianasy, Mirjana Povic,
 Monserrat Martinez, Motseothata Tisang, Muphulusi Nekhavhambe,
 Namrata Roy, Narendranath Layek, Narges Hatamkhani, Nceba Mhlahlo,
 Nicole Thomas, Norman Grogin, Ny Ando Ralitera, Olena Bannikova,
 Olga Borodina, Osase Omoruyi, Pallavi Patil, Peixin Zhu,
 Petr Kurfürst, Petri Vaisanen, Philip Edwards, Prajval Shastri,
 Precious Sejake, Preeti Kharb, Qingling Ni, Raffaella Morganti,
 Rajan Chhetri, Roberto Assef, Roberto De Propris, Roman Todorov,
 Ruben Andreatsyan, Rukaiya Khatoon, S. Komossa, Salmoli Ghosh,
 Sarah Casura, Sarah White, Satish Sonkamble, Sergio Abraham Dzib Quijano,
 Shelley-Anne Harrisberg, Shilpa Sarkar, Shimeles Mengistue,
 Siham Kalli, Simone Veronese, Sofía Rojas Ruiz, Sophia van der Dussen,
 Soumyadeep Das, Stas Shabala, Stephanie Juneau, Sthabile Kolwa,
 Susan Ridgway, Sushant Dutta, Swetha Sankar, Takafumi Tsukui,
 Tej Chand, Thando Mothogoane, Thephilus Matsepane, Thiago Goncalves,
 Thunyapong Mahapol, Tolu Biressa, Tombo Fitahiana Rarivoarinoro,
 Tommaso Zana, Tong Su, Trystan Lambert, Valeriya Frolova,
 Venkatesh Ramakrishnan, Vida Saeedzadeh, William Welsh, Yu-Sik Kim,
 Yunyi Choi, Yuri Kovalev.

Gender Representation among Symposium Participants

All Symposium Participants via country of residence

8. 45 COUNTRIES REPRESENTED:

Algeria, Armenia, Australia, Austria, Botswana, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, Chile, China, Colombia, Côte D'Ivoire, Czech Republic, Egypt, Ethiopia, Finland, Germany, Ghana, Greece, Hong Kong, India, Iran, Italy, Japan, Kenya, Madagascar, Mexico, Namibia, Nepal, Netherlands, Nigeria, Poland, Republic of

Korea, Russia, Slovakia, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Tanzania, Thailand, Turkiye, Uganda, United Kingdom, United States, and Zimbabwe.

Due to incomplete data provided via the registration forms, we made some inferences (with regard to nationality) when constructing the following two charts:

Contributed Speakers via nationality

Contributed talks via Nationality, grouped by Continent

We note that it is important to record nationality in addition to the country of residence (i.e. affiliation) because the former tends to reflect a person's ethnicity whereas the latter is modulated by where there is more funding in Astronomy.

Contributed talks via Country of Residence, grouped by Continent

9. FINAL SCIENTIFIC PROGRAMME, INCLUDING CONTRIBUTING SPEAKERS:

Session name	Time (SAST)	Description
S 394-1 Poster session (Aug 13th)	10:00-10:30	Poster Session, with Chair: Sthabile Kolwa
S 394-1 (Aug 13th)	10:30-12:00	<p>Session Chair: Miriam Nyamai</p> <p>10:30 - 10:55 Invited review talk by Prof. Roberto Assef [he], <i>The Host Galaxies of Luminous Quasars</i></p> <p>10:55 - 11:10 Oral presentation by Qingling Ni [she], <i>The incidence of AGN in galaxies with different stellar population ages: probing SMBH fueling mechanisms throughout the galaxy lifecycle</i></p> <p>11:10 - 11:25 Oral presentation by Tommaso Zana [he], <i>Where do high-z quasars live?</i></p> <p>11:25 - 11:40 Oral presentation by Thando Mothogoane [she], <i>Investigating black-hole fuelling and star-formation for radio-AGN and SFG in the COSMOS field</i></p> <p>11:40 - 11:55 Oral presentation by Allison Man [she] (virtual), <i>A panchromatic view of the circumgalactic medium surrounding a brightest cluster galaxy at z=0.4</i></p>

<p>S 394-2</p> <p>(Aug 13th)</p>	<p>13:30-15:00</p>	<p>Session Chair: Lerothodi Leeuw</p> <p>13:30 - 13:45 Oral presentation by Takafumi Tsukui [he], <i>Using ALMA as a Thermometer for Host Galaxy Growth of Quasar</i></p> <p>13:45 - 14:00 Oral presentation by Raffaella Morganti [she], <i>Radio jets expanding in gas-rich ISM: using cold gas to trace their impact</i></p> <p>14:00 - 14:15 Oral presentation by Leon Mtshweni [he], <i>Was the recent AGN activity of PKS 2014-55 triggered by a merger?</i></p> <p>14:15 - 14:30 Oral presentation by Olga Borodina [she], <i>The Role of Active Galactic Nuclei in Galaxy Evolution: How do jets propagate through the turbulent Interstellar Medium?</i></p> <p>14:30 - 14:45 Oral presentation by Ignacio del Moral-Castro [he], <i>Investigating the nuclear activity in the least dense regions of the nearby Universe</i></p> <p>14:45 - 15:00 Oral presentation by Kartik Sheth [he], <i>Inclusion, Diversity, Equity and Accessibility in Action</i></p>
<p>S 394-2</p> <p>Poster session</p> <p>(Aug 13th)</p>	<p>15:00-15:30</p>	<p>Poster Session, with Chair: Kabelo Kesebonye</p>
<p>S 394-3</p> <p>(Aug 13th)</p>	<p>15:30-17:00</p>	<p><i>Discussion session on Indigenous Astronomy, Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion, with Chair: Pfesemani van Zyl</i></p> <p>Panel members: Prof. Jarita Holbrook [she], Prof. Debra Meyer [she], Prof. Prajval Shastri [they/she],</p>

		Associate Prof. Jorge Moreno [they/he], and Dr Alfredo Carpineti [he]
S 394-3 Poster session (Aug 14th)	10:00-10:30	Poster Session, with Chair: Kabelo Kesebonye
S 394-4 (Aug 14th)	10:30-12:00	<p>Session Chair: Lucia Marchetti</p> <p>10:30 - 10:55 Invited talk by Dr Nicole Thomas [she], <i>Radio galaxies in cosmological simulations</i></p> <p>10:55 - 11:10 Oral presentation by Atsushi Hoshi [he], <i>The relationship between SMBHs and their host galaxies at intermediate redshift in the variability-selected AGN sample</i></p> <p>11:10 - 11:25 Oral presentation by Jacques Smulders [he], <i>Goal-Oriented Stacking: Selection of AGN Host Galaxies below the Radio Detection Threshold</i></p> <p>11:25 - 11:40 Oral presentation by Peixin Zhu [she], <i>Separating Star Formation, Active Galactic Nuclei, and Shocks in Galaxies</i></p> <p>11:40 - 11:55 Oral presentation by León Salas [he], <i>High-resolution insights into black hole accretion dynamics and jet phenomena</i></p>
S 394-5 (Aug 14th)	13:30-15:00	<p>IAUS 394 All-inclusive AGN (hybrid session)</p> <p>Extended e-poster session and networking.</p>

<p>S 394-4 Poster session (Aug 14th)</p>	<p>15:00-15:30</p>	<p>Poster Session, with Chair: Kenda Knowles</p>
<p>S 394-6 (Aug 14th)</p>	<p>15:30-17:00</p>	<p>Session Chair: Roberto De Propriis</p> <p>15:30 - 15:45 Oral presentation by Eckhard Sturm [he], <i>Spatially Resolving Active Galactic Nuclei at Low and High Redshift with the VLTI and GRAVITY</i></p> <p>15:45 - 16:00 Oral presentation by Elena Nokhrina [she], <i>Core-shift in parabolic accelerating jets – magnetic field assessment at gravitational radius</i></p> <p>16:00 - 16:15 Oral presentation by Erandi Chavez [she], <i>Prospects of Detecting a Jet in Sagittarius A* with VLBI</i></p> <p>16:15 - 16:30 Oral presentation by Soumyadeep Das [he], <i>The LOFAR Two-Metre Sky Survey: Unveiling the nature of the faint source populations and identifying underlying AGN with Prospector</i></p> <p>16:30 - 16:45 Oral presentation by Venkatesh Ramakrishnan [he], <i>Accretion flows and photon rings in nearby Universe</i></p> <p>16:45 - 17:00 Oral presentation by Georgios Filippou Paraschos [he], <i>Investigating magnetic launching of black hole jets with the Event Horizon Telescope</i></p>

<p>S 394-7</p> <p>(Aug 14th)</p>	<p>19:00-20:30</p>	<p>Session Chair: Dr Vanessa Moss, with this entire evening session being delivered remotely</p> <p>19:00 - 19:25 Invited talk by Dr Dylan Nelson [he] - <i>The impact of AGN feedback in cosmological galaxy formation simulations</i></p> <p>19:25 - 19:40 Oral presentation by Aditya J.N.H.S. [he] - <i>AGN feedback on neutral gas</i></p> <p>19:40 - 19:55 Oral presentation by Namrata Roy [she], <i>Violent feedback-driven winds from high redshift Radio loud AGNs revealed by JWST</i></p> <p>19:55 - 20:10 Oral presentation by Vida Saeedzadeh [she], <i>Dual AGNs: Detecting bright AGN pairs onto the path to binary black holes and black hole mergers</i></p> <p>20:10 - 20:25 Oral presentation by Jack Livingston [he], <i>MOJAVE XXII: The Spatial and Temporal Evolution of Faraday Rotation in AGN jets</i></p>
<p>Plenary</p> <p>(Aug 15th)</p>	<p>8:30-10:00</p>	<p>Plenary talk (given remotely) by Dr Beatriz Mingo [she], <i>Multiwavelength classification in the age of Big Data</i>, with Chair: Dr Sthabile Kolwa</p>
<p>S 394-5</p> <p>Poster session</p> <p>(Aug 15th)</p>	<p>10:00-10:30</p>	<p>Poster Session, with Chair: Kenda Knowles</p>

<p>S 394-8</p> <p>(Aug 15th)</p>	<p>10:30-12:00</p>	<p>Session Chair: Mirjana Povic</p> <p>10:30 - 10:45 Oral presentation by Eli Kasai [he], <i>Redshift Measurement of Gamma-Ray Blazars for the Cherenkov Telescope Array</i></p> <p>10:45 - 11:00 Oral presentation by Yuri Kovalev [he], <i>Radio-neutrino studies of blazars: inspiring progress and exciting opportunities</i></p> <p>11:00 - 11:15 Oral presentation by Emily Kerrison [she], <i>Hunting down young radio AGN with bayesian SED fitting</i></p> <p>11:15 - 11:30 Oral presentation by Precious Sejake [she], <i>SALT spectroscopic follow-up of the G4Jy Sample</i></p> <p>11:30 - 11:45 Oral presentation by Rajan Chhetri [he], <i>Studying population changes in sub-arcsecond scale active galactic nuclei at low radio frequencies</i></p> <p>11:45 - 12:00 Oral presentation by Ann Njeri [she], <i>Exploring the resolve μJy extragalactic radio source population at high resolution with wide-field VLBI surveys and paving the way for SKA</i></p>
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<p>S 394-9</p> <p>(Aug 15th)</p>	<p>13:30-15:00</p>	<p>Session Chair: Stas Shabala</p> <p>13:30 - 13:55 Invited talk by Dr Jan Scholtz [he], <i>Search for AGN in the early Universe with JWST</i></p> <p>13:55 - 14:10 Oral presentation by Luis Ho [he], <i>The Connection Between AGNs and Galaxies at $z > 3.5$ Revealed by JWST</i></p> <p>14:10 - 14:25 Oral presentation by Monserrat Martinez [they/she], <i>The role of AGN in regulating galaxy evolution in massive $z \sim 3-4$ galaxies</i></p> <p>14:25 - 14:40 Oral presentation by Marina Arnaudova [she], <i>Exploring the radio-loudness of SDSS quasars with spectral stacking</i></p> <p>14:40 - 14:55 Oral presentation by Anelise Audibert [she], <i>A multi-wavelength view of AGN feedback impact on the central kiloparsecs of galaxies</i></p>
<p>S 394-6</p> <p>Poster session</p> <p>(Aug 15th)</p>	<p>15:00-15:30</p>	<p>Poster Session, with Chair: Kenda Knowles</p>

<p>S 394-10</p> <p>(Aug 15th)</p>	<p>15:30-17:00</p>	<p>Session Chair: Andrea Caproni</p> <p>15:30 - 15:45 Oral presentation by Jason Shingirai Makechemu [he], <i>Deep-learning classifications of galaxy morphologies in large JWST surveys</i></p> <p>15:45 - 16:00 Oral presentation by Sofía Rojas Ruiz [she], <i>Finding and Characterizing AGN in the Epoch of Reionization with JWST NIRSpec Spectroscopy</i></p> <p>16:00 - 16:15 Oral presentation by Blessing Musiimenta [she], <i>Incidence and energetics of AGN outflows in X-ray selected samples</i></p> <p>16:15 - 16:30 Oral presentation by Donaji Esparza Arredondo [she], <i>JWST reveals the multi-phase outflow of the Seyfert galaxy MCG-05-23-16</i></p> <p>16:30 - 16:45 Oral presentation by James Chibueze [he], <i>Polarization analysis of the 2nd brightest radio galaxy MRC 0600-399 in Abell 3376 Galaxy Cluster</i></p> <p>16:45 - 17:00 Oral presentation by Salmoli Ghosh [she], <i>Unraveling the Drivers of Radio Outflows in Radio-Quiet AGNs: Insights from Magnetic Field Topology</i></p>
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10. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY:

Active galactic nuclei (AGN) play a crucial role in galaxy evolution through a range of feedback processes between the central supermassive black-hole and its surroundings. With the support of the following organisations:

- [IAU Division J](#) (Galaxies and Cosmology)
- [IAU Division B](#) (Facilities, Technologies and Data Science)
- [IAU Division C](#) (Education, Outreach and Heritage)

- The African Astronomical Society, [AfAS](#)
- The South African Astronomical Observatory, [SAAO](#)
- The South African Radio Astronomy Observatory, [SARAO](#)
- The European Southern Observatory, [ESO](#)

... we discussed the latest results in observation- and simulation-driven studies, covering both multi-wavelength and multi-messenger astronomy over a wide range of spatial scales and timescales. In particular, we showcased work that uses southern-hemisphere telescopes such as MeerKAT, SALT, H.E.S.S., ALMA, and the VLT, in addition to exciting, new observations from JWST, EHT, and the Vera C. Rubin Observatory. Furthermore, we incorporated a discussion on equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) in Astronomy — which is pivotal for the whole community — because researchers may not commonly set aside time to participate in EDI talks or see the relevance of EDI initiatives. This Symposium (in Cape Town, South Africa) was an excellent 5-year follow-up to the first IAU Symposium to be held in Ethiopia in over 100 years (“Nuclear activity in galaxies across cosmic time”), and so continued to establish and develop international collaborations across and beyond the African continent.

Out of all of the Symposia and Focus Meetings of this year’s General Assembly, our Symposium received the highest number of abstracts, which were assessed by our diverse Scientific Organising Committee. We decided that contributed talks should be allocated time-slots of 15 minutes each (so that explanations of the method and findings were not rushed), and this resulted in a total of 40 contributed talks for inclusion in the scientific programme. Final decisions were made by the Decision Committee (Sarah White, Sthabile Kolwa, and Preeti Kharb), with consideration of scientific merit as well as demographic information (gender, career stage, nationality, and country of residence). The latter enabled us to provide a platform for people that are under-represented at Astronomy conferences, with the aim that the majority of contributions were from delegates in the early stages of their career.

Given the high number of submitted abstracts, it was imperative that we scheduled a 90-minute session dedicated to poster-viewing, so that the large number of posters were given sufficient visibility. (We note that the usual poster-viewing times, during the morning and afternoon breaks, may have been dominated by in-person delegates queuing for tea/coffee or visiting the bathroom.) Furthermore, we were highly commended for organising an evening session where all presenters delivered their talks remotely. Not only did this ‘online-first’ approach show respect for our remote attendees, we demonstrated consideration of those in time-zones that differed from SAST (the nominal time-zone for the General Assembly). In addition, we showed that an interactive plenary talk is possible, with our plenary speaker (a fellow Astronomer for Planet Earth) attending online for environmental reasons.

Contributed talks by Gender

Contributed talks by Career Stage

(For the 'Career Stage' field, we defined 'Early-career' as the person being within their first or second postdoctoral position, and 'Mid-career' as the person being within their third, or more, postdoctoral position. Where this information was not provided via the abstract form, we consulted online information provided by the delegate through personal or departmental webpages.)

11. SCIENCE HIGHLIGHTS:

- A reminder that AGN variability may mean that black-hole mass estimates are not accurately determined.
- Development of a new BPT diagram that disentangles shocks induced by AGN activity and shocks induced by star-forming processes.
- Analytic simulations are able to incorporate turbulence created through convection.
- Optical interferometry from GRAVITY is enabling the size of the broad-line region to be measured directly, with most of the AGN suggesting the presence of a thick rotating disc of clouds.
- Further characterisation of the radio-jet profile through the Lorentz factor.
- Visibility simulations show that shorter baselines, than those available via current VLBI, are required for detecting radio jets. Furthermore, greater scattering of light at higher frequencies leads to lower detectability.
- A significant fraction of low-excitation radio-galaxies (LERGs) has been shown to have star-forming host galaxies.
- It is likely that jet launching has both Blandford-Znajek and Blandford-Payne mechanisms.
- Cosmological simulations, like TNG, are able to reproduce the optical-colour distribution that is observed across galaxy populations.
- A reminder to consider a separation threshold when comparing observations of dual AGN with simulations (since the former lack the required spatial resolution).
- Monthly monitoring of nearby radio-jets shows plasmoids colliding into each other and eventually having the same polarisation orientation as the outer part of the jet.
- There were several talks showing how JWST is enabling lower-mass supermassive black-holes to be detected at high redshift.
- It was argued that co-evolution of the black hole and its host galaxy may *not* take place at high redshift, with the latter growing at a later time.
- A reminder that radio-loud quasars tend to appear redder and have more [OII] emission (relative to star formation) than their radio-quiet counterparts.
- Whilst we observe evidence of quasar and radio-mode feedback, it may not be at the level to deplete the molecular-gas reservoir in the host galaxy.
- Polarisation in radio observations of radio-quiet AGN can enable quasar winds to be distinguished from small-scale radio-jets.

12. TOTAL AMOUNT OF GRANT FUNDS RECEIVED:

Total amount of grant funds via IAU Grants = 23,620 Euros

Total amount of grant funds via Africa Grants = 9,815 Euros

Total amount of grant funds via Simons-Foundation Grants = 8,920 Euros

Sum of additional grant money = 153,243 Rand = 8,126 Euros

13. NUMBER OF GRANT RECIPIENTS:

Number of IAU-Grant recipients = 37,

... so an average of 638 Euros per recipient

Number of Africa-Grant recipients = 24,

... so an average of 409 Euros per recipient

Number of Simons-Foundation-Grant recipients = 23,

... so an average of 388 Euros per recipient

Number of recipients of additional grant money = 8,

... so an average of 1,016 Euros per recipient

A total of 84 individuals received grants (irrespective of funding body)

Number of males: 44; Number of females: 37; Gender non-specific: 3

Prajval Shastri, Anelise Audibert, Alfredo Carpineti, Fabio Luchsinger,
Alberto Carramiñana, Bosco Oruru, Célestin Herbé-George,
Daudi Mazengo, Dejene Woldeyes, Dharam Lal, Proven-Adzri,
Eli Kasai, Eslam Elhosseiny, Evaristus Iyida, Gourab Giri, Harris Yao
Fortune Marc, Isreal Elijah, Jacques Smulders, James Chibueze,
Jason Makechemu, Julius Mathew, Mahdi Abdollahi, Mekuanint Kifle,
Mfuphi Ntshatsha, Michal Zajacek, Mingyu Ryu, Motseothata Tisang,
Narendranath Layek, Nceba Mhlahlo, Ny Ando Ralitera, Satish Sonkamble,
Shimeles Mengistue, Soumyadeep Das, Takafumi Tsukui, Tej Chand,
Thephilus Matsepane, Tommaso Zana, Trystan Lambert, Antoine Mahoro,
Muphulusi Nekhavhambe, Ahlam Farhan, Ann Njeri, Brenda Homera,
Debra Meyer, Dorcus Mulumba, Elena Nokhrina, Elizabeth Kamau,
Farideh Mazoochi, Janie du Preez, Jayde Bhana, Josephine Chishala,
Karina Santana, Kathleen Charlton, Katlego Mogamisi,
Khushboo Dixit, Marina Arnaudova, Matilde Signorini, Mehbuba Ahmed,
Miora Mbolatiana Randrianasy, Mirjana Povic, Monserrat Martinez,
Narges Hatamkhani, Pallavi Patil, Precious Sejake, Salmoli Ghosh,
Sarah White, Shilpa Sarkar, Siham Kalli, Sophia van der Dussen,
Thando Mothogoane, Tombo Fitahiana Rarivoarinoro, Vida Saeedzadeh,
Allison Man, Dylan Nelson, Ignacio del Moral-Castro, Luigi Barchiesi,
Peixin Zhu, Sthabile Kolwa, Tolu Biressa

Countries represented among the grant recipients:

Algeria, Australia, Austria, Botswana, Canada, Chile, Côte D'Ivoire, Egypt, Ethiopia, Finland, Germany, Ghana, India, Iran, Italy, Kenya, Madagascar, Mexico, Namibia, The Netherlands, Nigeria, Republic of Korea, Russia, Slovakia, South Africa, Spain, Tanzania, Turkiye, Uganda, United Kingdom, and United States.

14. ANONYMISED FEEDBACK FROM PARTICIPANTS:

“Judging from the quality of talks, and topics covered, I would count this as a very successful meeting!”

“I would like to give positive feedback from my personal side... I am participating virtually, because I have two very young kids and don't want to separate from them at the moment (I have done it for an observing trip, and it was not a good experience for the family). Traveling together is out of my budget ... So, for me, it was amazing to be able to participate virtually. The cherry on the cake top is that the virtual experience is amazing at IAU 2024. So Thank you for that. I appreciate that some people are very much into in person participation, but some situations in people's lives do not allow in person participation, which directly affects their competitiveness in CV, job market, future career paths. So having virtual attendance is a good option to, for example, me as a mother-academic at early stage of my career.”

“Just wanted to say hello and congratulate you and your team on the very successful conference.”

“It was an excellent meeting!”

15. RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Morning and afternoon breaks are already quite short (at 30 mins each), so we recommend an extended session for poster viewing. This is particularly welcomed by students and early-career researchers, who are most likely to be awarded poster presentations.
- In addition to preferred pronouns, we note that the career stage, nationality and country-of-residence should be *compulsory* fields within the registration form, so that these distributions can be assessed accurately. Our assessment was based on incomplete information that was provided as part of the travel-grant application, but not everyone applied for this.

- Furthermore, the registration form should ask for the participant's ethnicity via a compulsory field, as this (rather than nationality) can help to assess and mitigate racial bias during assessment of the submitted abstracts.
- Our EDI-dedicated session was very welcomed by participants, but incorporating such talks alongside science talks (rather than having a 'separate' session) was suggested as a way of improving the format of the Symposium. This is because, unfortunately, some delegates may still skip the EDI discussion entirely.
- As part of an 'online-first' approach of hybrid conferences, we highly recommend organising evening sessions. This is because catering for additional time-zones enables a wider geographical spread of online delegates to feel included in the conversation.

Slide credit: Kartik Sheth [he], Associate Chief Scientist, NASA

Overall Reflections

Two key ideas we rely on:

- **You can't be what you can't see**
- **You don't know what you don't know.**

Some takeaways from the work:

- **Critical to have leadership acknowledge the problem, take responsibility, pledge actions and ask to be held accountable.**
- Put people in positions of real leadership (don't focus solely on the pipeline)
- **Work hard to create inclusive and welcoming environment for all**
- Ensure one has attributes for solutions before jumping to solutions
- Avoid making assumptions
- **Ensure actions are impactful, measurable, sustainable**
- Evaluate and be ready to change tactics when necessary.
- **Focus on changing actions / behaviours**

16. ANTICIPATED NUMBER OF SEPARATE PAPERS IN THE PROCEEDINGS: 40+

17. REPORT SUBMITTED BY: Dr Sarah V. White and Dr Sthabile Kolwa

18. DATE AND PLACE: Cape Town and Johannesburg, South Africa

19. SIGNATURE OF SOC CHAIRS:

Dr Sarah V. White

Dr Sthabile Kolwa